

The role of knowledge networks in facilitating the creation of climate information services

Francesca Larosa and Marta Bruno-Soares

francesca.larosa@cmcc.it

Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC)

Ca' Foscari University

EMS 2021 Conference Award winner

DEFINE

KNs are informal groups of policy-makers, scientists, gov. agencies and NGOs that are in continuous contact to share and disseminate climate service

ASSESS

The purpose, process and audience of KNs spread globally, but working at different levels. Semi-structured interviews with 16 KNs.

The role of knowledge networks in facilitating the creation of climate information services

This work has been funded with the contribution of the EU H2020 CLARA project, Ref. 790482

Larosa Francesca and Marta Bruno-Soares

DERIVE

Different aims: capacity building for low-income countries and funding & network opportunities for EU and US. Still targeting mainly public sector. No shared understanding of what «effectiveness» is.

